

Speciation of Ternary Complexes of Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II) with L-Asparagine and L-Glycylglycine in Acetonitrile-water mixtures

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Abstract: Chemical speciation of ternary complexes of Ca(II), Zn(II) and Mn(II) with L-Asparagine and L-Glycylglycine was studied in various concentrations (0-60% v/v) of acetonitrile-water mixtures maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ at 303.0 K. Alkalimetric titrations were carried out with different relative concentrations (M: L: X = 1:2.5:2.5, 1:2.5:5.0, 1:5.0:2.5) of metal (M) to L- Asparagine (L) to L-Glycylglycine (X). Stability constants of ternary complexes were calculated and various models were refined with MINIQUAD75. The best-fit chemical models were selected based on statistical parameters and residual analysis. The trend of the variation in the stability constants with changing dielectric constant (D) of the medium was explained based on the electrostatic interactions of the ligands, charge neutralization, chelate effect, stacking interactions and hydrogen bonding. Distribution diagrams with pH at different compositions of aqua-organic mixtures and structures of plausible ternary complexes were also presented.

Keywords: Chemical speciation, Ternary complexes, Stability constants, Acetonitrile, MINIQUAD75.

I. INTRODUCTION

Most metabolic reactions are catalyzed by metal-containing enzymes, the activity of which is due to metal-enzyme-substrate complexes. The active site of the enzymes has a lower polarity than biofluids. The knowledge of the equivalent solution dielectric constant can throw light on the mechanism of the reaction. Further, intramolecular and ligand-ligand stacking interactions in mixed ligand complexes are favored in water-organic media, which reduce solution dielectric constant. Hence, modeling studies [1-4] involving ternary complexes have gained popularity in different aqua-organic mixtures with varying dielectric constants. The ternary complexes provide a model for the metal-directed reactions involving exchange of functional groups. The role of mixed-ligand complexes in biological processes has been well documented [5-6]. Calcium plays an important role in the cell membranes and as a structural component and also in muscle contraction [7]. It helps in blood clotting, nerve signaling and the release of certain hormones. Ca²⁺ ions are essential components of plant cell walls and cell membranes and are used to balance organic anions in the plant vacuole [8]. High calcium intake or absorption results in the development of kidney stones, but vitamin D is needed to absorb calcium [9-10]. Zinc plays vital role in biosystems [11-14]. It supports normal growth and development during pregnancy, childhood and adolescence and is required for proper sense of taste and smell [15-16]. Magnesium is involved in more than 300 metabolic reactions. It helps to regulate blood sugar levels, promotes normal blood pressure, and is known to be involved in energy metabolism and protein synthesis [17-18].

Acetonitrile (AN) is a colorless, polar aprotic solvent [19]. It has a relatively high dielectric constant ($\epsilon=36$) and a small autoprotolysis constant ($pK_s=33.6$). AN act as strongly differentiating solvent with a modest solvating power for many polar ionic solutes [20]. L-Asparagine is one of the 20 amino acids commonly found in animal proteins. The clinical use of L-asparaginase in the treatment of certain cancers [21-22] is based on the degradation of L-asparagine, which is required for cellular proliferation [23-24]. Glycylglycine (GG) is the simplest dipeptide made from the residues of two glycine molecules. Besides an important component of the tissue, glycylglycine is a potentially useful zwitterionic buffer in the physiological pH range (6.0 - 8.5).

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

0.05 mol L⁻¹ of L-Asparagine (Qualigens, India) and L-Glycylglycine (Qualigens, India) solutions were used. 0.10 mol L⁻¹ of Ca(II), Zn(II) and Mg(II) chlorides (Qualigens, India) were prepared by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. 0.40 mol L⁻¹ carbonate free sodium hydroxide (Qualigens, India) pellets were used for the preparation of solution. 2.0 mol L⁻¹ sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) solution was used to maintain 0.16 mol L⁻¹ ionic strength in the titrand. Acetonitrile (Qualigens, India) was used as a solvent. Triple distilled water was used throughout the experiment. The strengths of acid and alkali were determined using Gran plot method [25-26]. To assess the errors that might have crept in to the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one-way classification (ANOVA) [27].

III. PROCEDURE

ELICO-120 digital pH meter was used to perform alkalimetric titrations with varying compositions of AN (0.0-60.0% v/v) maintaining an ionic strength 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium chloride at 303.0±0.1 K. Amounts of L-Asparagine and L-Glycylglycine in the titrands are 0.250, 0.375 and 0.500 mmols. 0.05 mol L⁻¹ Potassium hydrogen phthalate and 0.01 mol L⁻¹ borax solutions were used to calibrate the pH meter. The glass electrode was equilibrated for several days in a well stirred AN-water mixture. Strong acid was titrated against alkali to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode at regular intervals. The calomel electrode was refilled with AN-water mixture of equivalent composition of the titrand.

IV. MODELING STRATEGY

The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode is accounted for in the form of correction factor which was computed from the simulated acid-base titration data calculated by SCPHD program [28-29]. Correction was applied to the pH meter dial reading by using correction factor. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares computer program, MINQUAD75 [30], which exploit the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of ternary systems, the correction factor, protonation constants of Asparagine and Glycylglycine and stability constants of binary complexes of metals with the ligands were fixed. Titrations were carried out in the presence of different relative concentrations of the metal (M) to Asparagine (L) and Glycylglycine (X) with 0.40 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. The analytical concentrations of the ingredients are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Total initial concentrations of ingredients (in mmol) for mixed-ligand titrations in 0.0–60.0% v/v AN–water mixtures

% v/v	AN	Ca(II)		TL0	Mg(II)		TL0	Zn(II)		M: L: X
		Asp	GG		Asp	GG		Asp	GG	
	0.0819	0.2495	0.2510	0.0879	0.2495	0.2510	0.0829	0.2495	0.2510	1:2.5:2.5
00.0	0.0819	0.3742	0.3765	0.0879	0.3742	0.3765	0.0829	0.3742	0.3765	1:2.5:5.0
		0.4990	0.5020		0.4990	0.5020		0.4990	0.5020	1:5.0:2.5
		0.2500	0.2475		0.2500	0.2475		0.2500	0.2510	1:2.5:2.5
10.0	0.0819	0.3750	0.3712	0.0879	0.3750	0.3712	0.0829	0.3750	0.3765	1:2.5:5.0
		0.5000	0.4950		0.5000	0.4950		0.5000	0.5020	1:5.0:2.5
		0.2495	0.2475		0.2495	0.2475		0.2495	0.2475	1:2.5:2.5
20.0	0.0819	0.3742	0.3712	0.0879	0.3742	0.3712	0.0829	0.3742	0.3712	1:2.5:5.0
		0.4990	0.4950		0.4990	0.4950		0.4990	0.4950	1:5.0:2.5
		0.2500	0.2500		0.2500	0.2500		0.2500	0.2500	1:2.5:2.5
30.0	0.0819	0.3750	0.3750	0.0879	0.3750	0.3750	0.0829	0.3750	0.3750	1:2.5:5.0
		0.5000	0.5000		0.5000	0.5000		0.5000	0.5000	1:5.0:2.5
		0.2495	0.2500		0.2500	0.2500		0.2500	0.2500	1:2.5:2.5
40.0	0.0819	0.3742	0.3750	0.0879	0.3750	0.3750	0.0829	0.3750	0.3750	1:2.5:5.0
		0.4990	0.5000		0.5000	0.5000		0.5000	0.5000	1:5.0:2.5
		0.2495	0.2500		0.2495	0.2495		0.2495	0.2500	1:2.5:2.5
50.0	0.0819	0.3742	0.3750	0.0879	0.3742	0.3742	0.0829	0.3742	0.3750	1:2.5:5.0
		0.4990	0.5000		0.4990	0.4990		0.4990	0.5000	1:5.0:2.5
		0.2500	0.2495		0.2500	0.2495		0.2500	0.2495	1:2.5:2.5
60.0	0.0819	0.3750	0.3742	0.0879	0.3750	0.3742	0.0829	0.3750	0.3742	1:2.5:5.0
		0.5000	0.4990		0.5000	0.4990		0.5000	0.4990	1:5.0:2.5

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Alkalimetric titrations of mixtures containing different mole ratios of Asparagine and Glycylglycine in presence of mineral acid and polar aprotic solvent inferred that MLX and MLXH species are formed for Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II). The parameters of the best-fit models and statistical parameters are given in Table 2. A very low standard deviation in $\log \beta$ values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} indicate that the model is consistent with the experimental data [31]. The kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic as well as platykurtic patterns and very few form mesokurtic patterns. The values of skewness show that the residuals form a part of normal distribution and hence least squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low

crystallographic R -factor values, which indicate the need for inclusion of additional species in the model. χ^2 is a special case of γ distribution which measures the probability of residuals forming a part of standard normal distribution.

Table 2 Parameters of the best-complexes of L-Asparagine and Mg(II) and Zn(II) in AN-water Ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹

AN % v/v	log β_{mlh} (SD)		pH-Range	NP	U_{corr} *10 ⁸	χ^2	Skew-ness	Kurt-osis	R-factor	
	1110	1111								
Ca(II)										
0.0	12.58(09)	20.14(04)		1.8-8.2	127	2.35	21.76	0.78	4.06	0.0049
10.0	8.66(38)	16.60(36)		2.8-10.0	19	2.97	14.56	-0.18	3.76	0.0274
20.0	6.98(49)	15.68(51)		1.9-9.6	137	2.12	50.51	1.27	3.29	0.0196
30.0	6.60(96)	15.85(69)		2.8-10.0	24	7.00	31.33	0.94	3.05	0.0508
40.0	6.01(93)	15.44(92)		2.9-9.8	23	19.41	54.43	1.18	4.14	0.0351
50.0	11.01(86)	*****		2.8-10.2	30	5.77	69.07	0.93	3.24	0.1303
60.0	8.24(88)	16.97(77)		2.6-8.2	32	3.85	56.69	0.90	2.42	0.0513
Mg(II)										
0.0	13.65(16)	20.63(05)		1.8-8.2	126	2.76	21.90	-0.27	4.88	0.0069
10.0	8.56(36)	16.56(33)		2.8-10.0	19	2.43	14.53	-0.18	3.76	0.0274
20.0	7.01(45)	15.78(57)		1.9-9.6	37	3.98	50.69	1.37	3.39	0.0197
30.0	6.00(94)	15.65(60)		2.8-10.0	57	7.31	40.00	1.52	3.05	0.0304
40.0	8.67(90)	16.90(80)		2.9-9.8	29	3.29	52.84	0.94	5.05	0.0665
50.0	10.69(89)	*****		1.8-8.0	38	2.29	56.50	0.97	2.45	0.0513
60.0	8.222(80)	16.79(71)		2.6-10.2	32	3.06	32.77	0.90	2.41	0.0508
Zn(II)										
0.0	9.23(18)	15.89(38)		1.8-8.2	40	8.75	30.59	1.32	3.52	0.0069
10.0	8.40(24)	15.47(53)		2.6-8.8	20	5.70	42.70	0.52	4.79	0.0185
20.0	8.44(52)	16.02(64)		2.8-9.8	86	3.41	57.40	0.66	3.97	0.0419
30.0	8.83(54)	15.83(67)		2.8-10.0	24	2.61	35.3	1.14	3.63	0.0382
40.0	8.67(81)	16.96(80)		2.9-9.8	23	6.16	41.72	1.52	5.07	0.0304
50.0	10.99(96)	*****		2.8-8.2	23	2.10	62.24	0.88	2.81	0.1310
60.0	8.15(90)	16.95(85)		2.5-10.5	34	3.63	60.71	0.94	2.36	0.0512

fit chemical models of ternary L-Glycylglycine with Ca(II), mixtures. Temperature = 303K,

A. Effect of solvent

AN is a dipolar aprotic non-aqueous positive and coordinating solvent. It is a structure breaker and it disrupts the water structure and forms AN-water complex. Variation of logarithmic values of stability constants ($\log \beta$) or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon the charge of the stern layer [32], polarity of the medium and the electrostatic attraction or repulsion. The linear variation (Figure 1) of stability constants of ASP and GG complexes of Ca(II), Mg(II), and Zn(II) in AN-water mixtures indicates that electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions. According to Born's classical treatment [33] the stability of the complex depends on accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constant. Hence, the $\log \beta$ values should vary linearly as a function of $1/D$ of the medium.

Figure 1: Variation of stability constants of ternary complexes with $1/D$ of AN-water mixtures (A) Ca(II) - (■) $\log \beta_{MLX}$, (●) $\log \beta_{MLXH}$; (B) Mg(II) - (■) $\log \beta_{MLX}$, (●) $\log \beta_{MLXH}$; and (C) Zn(II) - (■) $\log \beta_{MLX}$, (●) $\log \beta_{MLXH}$

B. Stability of ternary complexes

The change in stability of ternary complexes as compared to their binary analogues was quantified [34-37], based on the disproportionation constant ($\log X$) given by Equation 1.

$$\log X = 2 \log K_{MLX}^M - \log K_{ML_2}^M - \log K_{MX_2}^M \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

This corresponds to the equilibrium

$$\log X_{MLXH} = 2 \log \beta_{MLXH} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_2H} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Under the equilibrium conditions one can expect the formation of 50% ternary complexes and 25% each of the binary complexes statistically and the value of log X shall be 0.6 [38]. A value which is greater than this, accounts for the extra stability of MLX and MLXH.

Table 3: Calculation of log X values from overall stability constants. Equations for the calculation of log X

$$\Delta \log X_{MLXH} = 2 \log \beta_{MLXH} - \log \beta_{ML_2H} - \log \beta_{MX_2H} \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

$$\Delta \log X_{MLX} = 2 \log \beta_{MLX} - \log \beta_{ML_2} - \log \beta_{MX_2} \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

The log X values are calculated from binary and ternary complexes using the equations given in Table 3. Various possible log X values obtained from these equations are given in Table 4. These values could not be calculated for some systems due to the absence of relevant binary species. In the present study, the log X values range from 0.30 to 23.11 for Ca(II), 0.53 to 24.06 for Mg(II) and 0.30 to 20.05 for Zn(II) and all values are found to be higher than those expected on statistical bases (0.6). These higher values account for the extra stability of the ternary complexes. The reason [39] for the extra stability of these ternary complexes may be due to interactions outside the coordination sphere such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, charge neutralization, chelate effect and stacking interactions. The extra stability of ternary complexes makes them more amenable for metal transport. The less stable binary complexes make the metals bioavailable.

Table 4: log X values of mixed ligand complexes of Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II)-ASP and GG in AN-water mixtures calculated using binary constants and various possible equations given in Table 3

% v/v AN	MLXH	MLX	MLXH	MLX	MLXH	MLX
	Ca(II)		Mg(II)		Zn(II)	
00.0	14.02	1.01	17.78	3.82	12.32	1.1
10.0	23.11	2.23	24.06	6.06	13.84	0.30
20.0	18.19	0.79	18.07	0.53	15.58	0.44
30.0	18.80	0.30	20.01	2.22	17.70	3.97
40.0	18.18	1.12	21.96	5.55	19.55	2.97
50.0	****	6.03	****	5.57	****	4.74
60.0	19.70	2.24	20.36	3.62	20.05	2.45

C. Effect of Influential parameters on stability constant

An investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand and metal on stability constant. The results are given in Table 5. The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants

due to incorporation of errors is acid > alkali > Asparagine > Glycylglycine > metal. Some species were even rejected when errors were introduced in the concentrations. Rejection of species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors, confirms the appropriateness of the chosen best-fit models. This study also indicates the relative sensitivities of model parameters.

Table 5. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of ternary complexes of Ca(II) with L- Asparagine and L-Glycylglycine in 40% v/v AN-water mixture

Ingredient AN MIX	% Error	log β (SD)	
		1110	1111
	0	6.01(93)	15.44(92)
Alkali	-5	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	Rejected	15.77(33)
	2	11.51(32)	19.58(25)
	5	Rejected	Rejected
Acid	-5	Rejected	20.76(78)
	-2	11.46(28)	19.66(22)
	2	Rejected	16.83(28)
	5	Rejected	16.80(68)
Asp	-5	5.94(24)	13.87(45)
	-2	8.80(19)	16.84(16)
	2	7.99(96)	17.83(92)
	5	8.79(85)	17.96(83)
GG	-5	5.94(24)	13.87(45)
	-2	8.80(19)	16.84(16)
	2	7.99(96)	17.83(92)
	5	8.79(85)	17.96(83)
Metal	-5	9.13(73)	18.06(71)
	-2	9.03(81)	17.97(79)
	2	5.10(49)	14.18(83)
	5	4.86(52)	14.16(98)

D. Complex Equilibria and Distribution diagrams

Various possible equilibria for the formation of the ternary complexes refined in the present study have been proposed based on the existence of free metal, various forms of the ligands and the binary complexes as found in the distribution diagrams. Some typical distribution diagrams in 40% AN-water mixture were drawn by using the formation constants of the best fit model and are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Species distribution diagrams of ternary complexes of *L-Asparagine* and *L-Glycylglycine*: (A) Ca(II), (B) Mg(II) and (C) Zn(II) in 40% AN-water mixture.

They contain protonated and unprotonated ternary species like MLXH and MLX for Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II) in AN-water mixtures. The active forms of these ligands are LH_2^+ , LH and L^- for Asparagine and XH_2^+ , XH and X^- for Glycylglycine. The binary complex species of Asparagine and Glycylglycine are ML_2 , ML_2H and ML_2H_2 for Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II) in AN-water mixtures. The distribution diagrams indicate the relative abundance of various forms of chemical speciation at different pH and dielectric conditions. The increased concentrations of complexing agents make the essential metal ions unavailable due to the formation of stable binary metal complexes. The formation of the ternary complex species can be represented by the following equilibria.

For Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II) MLXH and MLX, species are formed in the pH range 2.0-11.0. For all the metal-ligand systems MLX species is formed by the deprotonation of MLXH (Equilibrium 13). Equilibrium 13 is more predominant for Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II) because

the percentage of MLXH is decreasing where the percentage of MLX is increasing. For MLXH species is formed by protonation of MXH association with LH_2 (Equilibrium 10) and MLH association with XH_2 (Equilibrium 9). Based on the protonation and deprotonation equilibria of Asparagine and Glycylglycine, depending on the coordinating sites in the ligands, nature of the metal ions and basic coordination chemistry principles, the possible structures of the ternary complexes are proposed as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Proposed structures of ternary complexes, where S = solvent or water; M = Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II)

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The species detected are MLX, and MLXH for Ca(II), Mg(II) and Zn(II) with Asparagine (L) and Glycylglycine (X). The values of $\Delta \log X$ indicate that the ternary species have extra stability compared to the binary species, may be due to the interactions outside the coordination sphere, such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, charge neutralization, chelate effect etc. The linear increase in the stabilities of ternary complexes with decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium is due to the dominance of electrostatic forces. The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is acid > alkali > ligand > metal .

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